

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ НАПРЯЖЕННО-ДЕФОРМИРОВАННОГО СОСТОЯНИЯ ЧАРВАКСКОЙ ПЛОТИНЫ С УЧЕТОМ ДАВЛЕНИЯ ВОДЫ

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STUDY OF THE STRESS-STRAIN STATE OF THE CHARVAK DAM CONSIDERING WATER PRESSURE

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В статье приведено исследование напряженно-деформированного состояния Чарвакской плотины с учетом давления воды. Решена упругая задача НДС Чарвакской плотины с учетом собственного веса, давления воды, основания. Получены изолинии напряжения, смещения, деформации и давления воды. Определены максимальные горизонтальные и вертикальные смещения. Максимальное смещение появляется в гребне плотины. Определено горизонтальное и вертикальное напряжение в теле плотины с учетом давления воды.

ABSTRACT

This article presents a study of the stress-strain state of the Charvak Dam accounting for water pressure. The elastic problem related to the stress-strain state of the Charvak Dam is addressed considering its own weight, water pressure, and foundation. Isolines of stresses, strains, displacements, and water pressure are plotted. The maximum horizontal and vertical displacements are identified, with the peak displacement occurring at the crest of the dam. The horizontal and vertical stresses within the dam body are assessed with consideration of water pressure.

Ключевые слова: напряженно-деформированное состояние, плотина, давление воды, геометрические и физико-механические характеристики, расчетная схема, изолинии напряжения, смещение, деформация.

Keywords: stress-strain state, dam, water pressure, geometric and physical-mechanical characteristics, calculation scheme, stress isolines, displacement, strain.

Introduction. Dams are critical engineering structures that provide a water supply, generate electricity, and help prevent flooding. However, operating a dam comes with significant risks, including the potential for earthquakes. The impact of earthquakes can result in severe damage to dam structures, leading to serious environmental and social consequences. As a result, ensuring the stability of dams is essential during both project development and ongoing maintenance. In the past decade, the global scientific community has made substantial advancements in studying methods to enhance the reliability of dams. This includes the use of modern building materials, computer modeling, and advanced techniques for analyzing potential hazards.

Modern approaches to the design and analysis of dam strength. Key research focuses on the methods for assessing the strength of dams using modern computing technologies. Reference [1] discusses how dams respond

to various loads, highlighting the significance of considering the interaction between the foundation, structure, and water level. The finite element model introduced in [1] is beneficial for conducting further dynamic analyses.

The study referenced in [2] focuses on the stability of earth dams under seismic loading through three-dimensional modeling. The software developed in this study enables effective analysis of dynamic processes and highlights the differences between conventional two-dimensional and three-dimensional methods. The impact of water seepage on the aging of concrete dams is discussed in [3]. This study presents a chemical-mechanical model that predicts changes in the mechanical properties of concrete. The model has been successfully applied to calculate the deformation of super-tall arch dams, indicating an increase in the maximum annual strain of 0.65 mm after a century of operation.

Reference [4] discusses the monitoring of micro-cracks in concrete dams, highlighting how the formation of

these cracks can lead to a decrease in structural integrity, stability, and water tightness. A comprehensive monitoring system was developed for a roller-compacted concrete (RCC) gravity dam construction site, incorporating acoustic emission, micro-seismic measurements, acoustic wave detection, crack sensors, and strain gauges. This system enables the evaluation of both micro- and macro-crack development. However, the sensitivity of the acoustic emission method was found to be lower than that of the micro-seismic method. Despite detecting micro-crack signals, no significant macro-crack expansions were observed. Overall, the multi-sensor system effectively monitors crack behavior in large concrete structures.

Risk assessment and seismic stability. The seismic safety of dams remains a critical concern, particularly in regions with high tectonic activity. Reference [5] introduces a probabilistic risk analysis method that utilizes Monte Carlo simulations to account for uncertainties in soil parameters and loading conditions. Additionally, a Bayesian approach is employed to minimize uncertainties in assessing seismic vulnerability. This method was tested on a concrete dam in Italy. In reference [6], various methods for simplifying the geometry of structures used in the stability analysis of arch dams are discussed. The stability of earth dams is addressed in reference [7], where the authors propose techniques to strengthen foundations and evaluate the effects of seismic waves. These reinforcement methods enhance resistance to failure during earthquakes. Innovative strategies for improving the seismic resilience of dams are outlined in reference [8]. They involve creating specialized layers from recycled car tires, which would enhance vibration absorption and decrease the structural load.

Dam condition monitoring and diagnostics. Modern monitoring technologies are crucial in ensuring dam safety. Article [9] demonstrates the effectiveness of installing pressure and deformation sensors, highlighting their high accuracy in real-time monitoring. The use of seismic equipment plays an important role in identifying risks and planning for modernization. Digital devices record the intensity of tremors, which aids in understanding the aftermath of earthquakes. In [10], the application of drones for inspecting hard-to-reach areas of dams is discussed, enhancing damage diagnostics. Additionally, machine learning is being actively implemented. Article [11] proposes a model for predicting dam deformations based on the analysis of sensor data. This model outperforms conventional methods by taking into account complex physical characteristics and hysteresis effects, thereby increasing the reliability of predictions and contributing to the safe operation of dams.

Development prospects. Researchers are increasingly focusing on integrating environmental and engineering solutions in dam construction. Adapting structures to climate change and utilizing 3D printing technologies for producing high-strength concrete are crucial developments. The creation of digital twins of dams is advancing, allowing accurate predictions of their behavior. References [12–15] explore how geology and seismic activity impact dam deformations, highlighting the influence of soil mechanics based on the type of material and loading conditions. Laboratory

experiments underscore the necessity for exact assessment of soil mechanical properties to ensure the design of stable structures.

An analysis of publications from the last decade indicates that dam strength research focuses on several key areas: the introduction of innovative materials, improvements in numerical modeling methods, enhancements in seismic stability, and the development of monitoring systems. Prospects include the integration of environmental factors, adaptation to climate change, and the application of advanced technologies such as machine learning and 3D printing. These advancements present new opportunities for enhancing the reliability and durability of hydraulic structures.

This article explores modern methods for assessing dam strength and highlights promising research areas within this field. It emphasizes analyzing current regulatory documents and calculation approaches, as well as new technologies and methods that enhance the reliability and safety of dams in regions with high seismic activity.

Modern methods of dam strength assessment. Regulatory documents and standards. The seismic resistance of dams is assessed based on international and national standards and recommendations. One of the main documents is the European standard EN 1998-1 "Design of structures for seismic action", which establishes general principles for the design of buildings and structures, including dams. In Russia, SNiP II-7-81* "Construction in seismic areas" is used, which contains requirements for the design and construction of buildings and structures in areas of high seismicity. In addition, there are specialized regulatory documents, such as FEMA P-750 "Guidelines for the assessment of seismic resistance of dams" (USA) and ICOLD Bulletin 72 "Analysis of seismic resistance of concrete dams". These documents contain recommendations for conducting calculations and tests, as well as for the selection of materials and design solutions that ensure the necessary resistance of dams to earthquakes.

Calculation methods. Various calculation methods are used to assess the strength of dams, ranging from simple analytical models to complex numerical methods. The most common methods are:

1. Limit state method. This method is based on determining the critical state of the structure under seismic impact. It allows estimating the probability of dam destruction or damage at a given earthquake intensity.

2. Dynamic analysis. This method includes modeling the dam's behavior over time under the influence of seismic waves. This allows considering not only static loads, but also dynamic effects such as resonance phenomena and inertial forces.

3. Numerical modeling. The use of modern software packages such as PLAXIS, ANSYS, ABAQUS, and LS-DYNA allows conducting a detailed analysis of the stress-strain state of the dam under seismic action. Numerical models take into account the nonlinearity of the material, the contact interaction of structural elements, and other factors affecting the structure's behavior.

Experimental studies. Experimental studies are crucial for validating theoretical calculations and developing

new technologies to ensure the dam's safety. The primary types of experiments include:

1. Modeling with physical models. Creating small-scale prototypes of dams and testing them on vibration tables provides data on how the structures behave under various seismic loads.

2. Full-scale tests. Conducting full-scale tests on actual dams allows for an assessment of the earthquake protection systems in real-world conditions.

3. Monitoring and diagnostics. Installing sensors and monitoring systems on operated dams enables the acquisition of real-time data about the state of the structure, facilitating the prompt identification of potential issues.

After analyzing and reviewing the current state of technology in the calculation of earth structures globally, we conclude that PLAXIS 2D is a highly effective tool for geotechnical analysis, particularly for two-dimensional modeling of soil and rock deformations and stability. Its user-friendly interface, robust calculation capabilities, and support for a variety of material models, such as Mohr-Coulomb and Hardening Soil, make it a popular choice among engineers worldwide. The software is capable of handling complex issues related to excavations, embankments, foundations, tunnels, and seismic loads. Furthermore, PLAXIS 2D excels in calculating the stress-strain state (SSS) of dams thanks to its focus on geotechnical modeling. It effectively accounts for complex soil conditions, construction stages, and hydrostatic loads, all of which are essential for comprehensive dam analysis.

Here are the key aspects of using PLAXIS 2D for such tasks:

- Flexibility of material models (it supports Mohr-Coulomb, Hardening Soil (HS), Soft Soil, Jointed Rock, and other models, which allow accurately describing the behavior of soils and dam materials; Hardening Soil is especially useful for modeling the nonlinear behavior of soils under load, which is important for high dams);

- Accounting for construction stages (PLAXIS allows modeling the sequential construction of a dam (layer-by-layer construction), which reflects the real process and affects the SSS; the extent of soil saturation with water can be set, taking into account pore pressure);

- Hydrostatic and hydrodynamic loads (the program allows modeling filtration processes (for example, using the PLAXIS 2D Flow module), which is important for analyzing pore pressure and filtration stability of a dam; the ability to consider seismic loads to assess the SSS under dynamic effects);

- Interfaces and interactions (contact elements between materials (e.g., soil-dam or core-shell) could be set to simulate friction and cohesion; consideration of reinforcement elements (geotextiles, anchors) for reinforced dams);

- Stability analysis (the $c-\phi$ reduction method is used to estimate the stability factor of dam slopes; it allows identifying potential failure zones).

Features in calculating the SSS of dams:

- Soil conditions: An accurate geological model is required, including data on compressibility, strength, and filtration properties of soils. PLAXIS allows defining complex stratigraphic profiles.

- Pore pressure: For earth and fill dams, it is important to consider water filtration, especially at high reservoir levels. The Flow module helps to model steady and unsteady flows.

- Dynamic loads: For seismically active zones, the PLAXIS dynamic module can be used to analyze the stress-strain state during earthquakes.

- Long-term deformations: The Soft Soil Creep model is suitable for assessing soil creep, which is relevant for clayey cores of dams.

Results of calculations performed for the Charvak dam using the PLAXIS2D software package.

The geometric and physical-mechanical characteristics are as follows: dam height is 168 m, cross-section length is 664 m, crest width is 12 m, core height is 160 m, core cross-section length is 110 m, core upstream width is 10 m. Specific gravity of the prism is 19.8 kN/m³, specific gravity of the core is 17.8 kN/m³, modulus of elasticity of the prism is 60 MPa, modulus of elasticity of the core is 30 MPa, Poisson's ratios of the dam and core are 0.3, prism filtration coefficient is 100 m/day, core filtration coefficient is $1 \cdot 10^{-5}$ m/day.

The calculation scheme is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Calculation scheme of the Charvak earth dam

The elastic problem of the Charvak dam's stress-strain state (SSS) is analyzed by taking into account its weight, water pressure, and foundation conditions. We have obtained isolines representing stresses, displacements, strains,

and water pressure. In Figure 2, the isolines of vertical displacements in the dam's cross-section are displayed. The maximum vertical displacement occurs at the dam's crest, measuring 41.5 mm. From this graph, we can observe that

vertical displacement values decrease continuously from the top to the bottom of the dam. Figure 3 illustrates the isolines of horizontal displacements within the same cross-section. The horizontal displacements on the left side of the dam's prism are directed along the left edge, with a maximum value of 4 mm. The horizontal displacements on the

right side of the prism also follow the right edge, reaching a maximum of 6.5 mm. The maximum horizontal displacement occurs at the crest of the dam, where it measures 7.0 mm.

Fig. 2. Isolines of vertical displacements of the Charvak earth dam

Fig. 3. Isolines of horizontal displacements of the Charvak earth dam

Figure 4 illustrates the isolines of vertical stresses across the dam's cross-section. The maximum vertical stress, measuring 4.52 MPa, occurs at the base of the dam core. The graph indicates that vertical stresses on the slopes are zero, and they rise continuously from the top to the bottom. A sharp change in vertical stresses occurs at the boundary between the core and the prism, where jumps are observed. This is due to the difference in material properties; the core soil is softer and has a lower specific gravity

compared to the prism soil. Figure 5 presents the isolines of horizontal stresses in the cross-section of the dam. The maximum horizontal stress appears at the base of the dam core, with a value of 2.36 MPa. Similar to the vertical stresses, the horizontal stresses on the slopes are zero and increase steadily from top to bottom. At the core-prism boundary, there is also a sharp change in horizontal stress values, reflecting the differences in the materials of the core and prism.

Fig. 4. Isolines of vertical stresses of the Charvak earth dam

Fig. 5. Isolines of horizontal stresses of the Charvak earth dam

Conclusion. The stress-strain state of the Charvak earth dam is analyzed, taking into account its own weight and water pressure. The maximum horizontal and vertical displacements are determined. The maximum displacement appears in the dam crest. The horizontal and vertical stresses in the dam body are determined considering water pressure.

Ensuring the strength and safety of dams is a vital concern that requires a comprehensive approach. Contemporary strength assessment methods, which combine theoretical calculations, experimental studies, and the application of new technologies, can significantly enhance the reliability and safety of these structures. Continued scientific research and the improvement of regulatory standards will

aid in the development of more stable and secure dams capable of withstanding seismic events.

This article was supported by budgetary funding from the Institute of Mechanics and Seismic Stability of Structures named after M.T. Urzbaev of the Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences.

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